

Effect of timing of basal N application on transplanted rice yield and N recovery

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We studied effect of timing of basal N application on grain yield and N recovery of transplanted rice during 1990 and 1991 kharif (monsoon) seasons. Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.3, bulk density 1.33 Mg/m³, 0.7% organic C, and CEC 17.9 c mol/kg.

Experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications (see table for treatments). We transplanted 25-d-old seedlings of variety HPH741 and applied recommended doses of phosphate and potash at 17.6 kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha. Half of the

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Treatment	Rice grain yield (t/ha)		Fertilizer recovery (%)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
N applied at transplanting	6.0	5.7	37.5	36.8
N applied at 7 DT ^a	6.1	6.1	43.6	44.3
N applied at 14 DT	6.9	7.1	55.9	57.2
N applied at 21 DT	6.1	6.4	44.2	46.1
N applied at 28 DT	6.4	6.0	36.7	35.9
N applied at 35 DT	5.9	5.6	35.1	34.7
LSD (0.05)	ns ^b	2.1	3.0	3.0

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bns = not significant.

recommended dose of 90 kg N/ha as urea was applied basally as per treatments; remaining N was applied at panicle initiation. Rainfall was 710.9, 419.3, 278.1, and 2.2 mm in 1990 and 98.6, 322.8, 40.1, and 1.2 mm in 1991 during Jul, Aug, Sep, and Oct, respectively.

Basal N applied 14 d after transplanting (DT) produced the most rice, which was significantly different from other treatments in 1991 only. The lower N recovery and grain yield observed for N compared with basal N at 14 DT might be explained by greater leaching losses of N at transplanting (see table). ■

Retention and movement of applied Zn in rice soils

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We studied the retention and movement of applied Zn in rice soils as influenced by organic matter, N, and P. Soils used were a sandy clay (Aquic Haplustalf) with pH 6.4, 0.33 dS/m EC, 0.71% organic C, 0.08% total N, 0.22% total P, 0.32% total K, and 77.50 ppm total Zn, and a sandy loam (Vertic Haplustalf) with pH 8.2, EC 3.4 dS/m, 0.42% organic C, 0.04% total N, 0.12% total P, 0.22% total K, and 80 ppm total Zn.

Farmyard manure (FYM) at 0.5 and 1.0% on a soil-weight basis, urea at 30 and 60 ppm N and superphosphate at 6 and 12 ppm P were mixed with air-dried, sieved soil samples packed to a uniform bulk density of 1.3 g/cm³ in PVC columns (35 cm long × 5 cm wide).

Five ppm Zn was applied as ⁶⁵Zn radiotracer-tagged ZnSO₄ to the top of each column and leached with deionized water for 168 h. A constant water head of 2.5 cm above the soil

surface was maintained. Leachates were collected every 24 h during the period and monitored for radioactivity. Soil in the columns was then divided into three layers (0-5, 5-15, and >15 cm). Radioassay of soil samples and leachates was done on a gamma ray spectrometer with a NaI-Tl crystal scintillator.

More than 90% of Zn applied as ZnSO₄ remained in the top 0-5 cm layer in both soils. Very little Zn reached the lower layers (see figure).

Distribution of ⁶⁵Zn in soil columns.

Treatments of FYM, N, and P at the various levels had no effect on Zn movement. No radioactivity was detected in leachates, suggesting that applied Zn was not prone to leaching but rather to fixation. ■